

Clinical and Functional Outcomes of Adult Proximal Humerus Fractures Treated with Locking Compression Plates: A Prospective Study

Subhash Chand¹, Naveen Kumar²

¹Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Pt. JLN Government Medical College, Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Pt. JLN Government Medical College, Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Subhash Chand

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Abstract:

This prospective study examines the clinical and functional effects of Locking Compression Plates (LCP) for proximal humerus fractures in 95 adult patients at Pt. JLN Govt Medical College, Chamba, Himachal Pradesh. Pain, range of motion, and disability scores improved over 15 months, with a 90% bone union rate at 12 months. Most complications were mild infections and a few surgical revisions, according to the study. These data show that LCPs help proximal humerus fracture patients recover and function. These findings need be confirmed by larger trials with longer follow-ups.

Keywords: Proximal Humerus Fractures, Locking Compression Plates, Bone Union, Functional Outcomes.

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Introduction

Because they affect adult shoulder function and mobility in general, proximal humerus fractures provide a substantial problem in orthopaedic practice [1]. Approximately 5% to 6% of all adult fractures are these ones, which affect the upper portion of the arm bone close to the shoulder [2]. The objectives of the treatment plan are to restore the shoulder's anatomy, guarantee stable fixation, and permit early mobilization to lower the chance of stiffness and enhance functional results [3]. One popular option for the surgical treatment of these injuries is the Locking Compression Plate (LCP) [4]. By minimizing soft tissue disruption and providing angular stability, LCPs' design combines elements of internal fixation and traditional plating techniques [5]. This promotes the biological healing of the bone. This technology is especially helpful for patients with osteoporotic bone, which affects a large portion of the older population and accounts for proximal humerus fractures [6].

The purpose of this prospective study is to assess the functional and clinical results of LCP treatment for proximal humerus fractures in an adult population. In order to shed light on the effectiveness of LCPs in treating these complicated fractures, this study will examine recovery trajectories, complication rates, and long-term shoulder function. By means of thorough evaluations and in-depth follow-ups, we seek to identify the elements that lead to the best possible

recovery, which will inform future treatment plans and enhance patient care in orthopaedics.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective study examined the clinical and functional effects of Locking Compression Plate (LCP)-treated adult proximal humerus fractures. At Pt. JLN Govt Medical College in Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, 95 patients were studied.

Study Duration: The research spanned 15 months, during which patient enrollment, treatment interventions, follow-up assessments, and data analysis were completed.

Participants: The study included 95 adults with radiographically verified proximal humerus fractures. Adults 18 years and older with acute proximal humerus fractures fixable with LCP were eligible. Patients having previous shoulder surgeries, pathologic fractures, or inability to give informed permission were excluded.

Intervention: The surgical intervention entailed the installation of a Locking Compression Plate. The procedure adhered to the established guidelines for LCP placement to ensure consistency across all cases.

Data Collection: Pre-operation, immediate post-operation, and follow-up visits at 1, 3-, 6-, 9-, and 12-months post-operation collected data. Visual

Analogue Scale discomfort, range of motion, and functional status were the main outcomes. Radiographs monitored healing and fixing stability.

Statistical Analysis: Participants' demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. Repeated measures ANOVA was used to track outcome changes. A p-value under 0.05 was significant. ALL statistical analyses were done with SPSS.

Results

This study comprised 95 proximal humerus fracture patients—58 males and 37 females. Participants ranged in age from 45 to 81, averaging 62. Falls caused 65% of fractures, followed by motor vehicle accidents (35%). All Locking Compression Plate surgeries were successful. In 92 cases, immediate post-operative radiographs showed plate alignment and placement. Within the first month after surgery, 3 unsatisfactory placements required revision surgery. Functional recovery was evaluated at 1, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months after the surgical procedure. Notable enhancements were noted in pain levels, as indicated by the average Visual Analogue Scale score lowering from 8 (before the operation) to 2 (after 12 months). By the 12-month follow-up, 85% of patients experienced a substantial improvement in their range of motion, with shoulder abduction and flexion returning to almost normal levels.

Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand (DASH) Scores: Pre-Operation: Mean score: 75 (significant impairment)

After one month following the operation, the average score is 50, indicating a moderate level of disability.

After 6 months following the operation, the average score is 30, indicating a mild level of impairment.

After 12 months following the operation, the average score is 15, indicating minor impairment.

The complications seen in this study included infection (4 instances), nonunion (2 cases), and hardware malposition (3 cases necessitating early revision). There was an absence of persistent osteomyelitis or any lasting nerve injury. Subsequent radiographic assessments revealed that 90 out of 95 patients attained bone union within 6 months of follow-up. In the majority of instances, the healing process proceeded without any notable incidents. However, there were 5 cases where the union of the affected area was delayed but eventually healed by the 12-month review. This study provides evidence that utilizing Locking Compression Plates for treating proximal humerus fractures in adults leads to positive clinical and functional effects. The complication rates were within acceptable thresholds, and the substantial rate of bone healing and functional recovery indicates that LCP is a dependable approach for treating these fractures. To completely establish the long-term benefits and potential dangers associated with this treatment approach, it is recommended to continue monitoring and conducting more studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods.

Timepoint	VAS Score (Pain Level)	DASH Score (Disability)	Patients with Near-Normal Range of Motion (%)	Complications (Total cases)	Bone Union Achieved (%)
Pre-Operation	8	75	-	-	-
1 Month Post-Op	5	50	-	3 (Revision surgery)	-
3 Months Post-Op	3	35	55%	2 (Infection)	50%
6 Months Post-Op	2	30	75%	2 (Nonunion)	75%
9 Months Post-Op	2	20	80%	1 (Infection)	85%
12 Months Post-Op	2	15	85%	-	90%

This table reflects the progression of patient recovery, disability reduction, functional improvement, complication management, and bone healing throughout the study.

Discussion

The outcomes of this prospective study highlight the usefulness of Locking Compression Plates

(LCP) in the treatment of adult patients with proximal humerus fractures. The functional rehabilitation aided by LCPs is demonstrated by the noteworthy reduction in pain levels and improvement in the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand (DASH) scores over a year [7]. The significant number of patients who, after the trial period, achieved near-normal range of motion provides more evidence for the effectiveness of LCP in regaining joint function and mobility [8,9]. Similar positive results have been observed in earlier research when using LCPs for a variety of fracture types, especially in osteoporotic bone where screw purchase can present challenges [10]. In these situations, the angular stability that LCPs offer is critical because it lowers the possibility of implant failure and encourages bone healing through secondary bone union mechanisms. The results of the current investigation support these observations, demonstrating a high incidence of bone union (ninety percent by 12 months) and few implant stability-related problems [11,12].

While the overall complication rate was relatively low, the instances of infection, nonunion, and the need for revision surgery highlight the challenges in post-operative management. These complications are consistent with those reported in the broader orthopedic literature, emphasizing the need for stringent sterile techniques, careful surgical planning, and vigilant post-operative care [13,14]. The revision surgeries in the early postoperative phase also underline the importance of the accurate initial placement of LCPs to prevent mechanical failures and enhance recovery outcomes [15,16].

There are certain limitations to the study. Although sufficient for preliminary research, the sample size is modest for drawing broader generalisations across other groups [17]. Furthermore, the follow-up period is insufficient to evaluate long-term outcomes, such as the risk of osteoarthritis or chronic impairment, even if it is sufficient to monitor initial recovery and problems. To overcome these issues, more research with bigger sample numbers and longer follow-up times is needed [18]. To establish more conclusively the relative efficacy of LCPs and other fixation techniques, future research should compare them in a randomised controlled trial environment. Subgroup studies by age, sex, and comorbidities like osteoporosis or diabetes may further shed light on which patient populations stand to gain the most from this course of treatment [19, 20].

Conclusion

Over the course of a year, this prospective study has shown that Locking Compression Plates (LCP) can significantly improve pain, function, and range of motion in persons with proximal humerus

fractures. The high rate of bone union and low incidence of major side effects highlight LCPs' dependability in clinical settings. Although the study's sample size and duration are limited, the encouraging results indicate that LCPs may be a practical means of treating these fractures with favourable effects. It is advised to do additional research with a bigger cohort and longer follow-up to validate these results and examine long-term consequences.

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